

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

A systematic literature review of geographic information system in COVID-19 studies

Thi-Quynh Nguyen ^{1,*} and Thi-Thuy Ngo ²

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy and Nursing, East Asia University of Technology, Hanoi, Vietnam.

² Faculty of Nursing, Phenikaa University, Hanoi, Vietnam.

World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2023, 15(02), 157–163

Publication history: Received on 05 July 2023; revised on 13 August 2023; accepted on 16 August 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2023.15.2.0355>

Abstract

Geographic information science (GIS) has established itself as a distinct domain and incredibly useful whenever the research is related to geography, space, and other spatio-temporal dimensions. However, the applications of GIS in the study of COVID-19 remained limited. In this systematic literature review, the current applications of GIS in COVID-19 studies were assessed. A total of 50 research articles related to applications of GIS were systematically retrieved and reviewed. There thematic groups were grouped, namely

- The use of GIS for mapping COVID-19,
- How to assess the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economies and environment, and
- The assessment of the community vulnerability and risks during the pandemic.

It was found that GIS shows great importance in the study of COVID-19. The wide range of applications offered by GIS could significantly improve how we fight the COVID pandemic.

Keywords: Geographic Information System; Spatial analysis; Spatial statistics; Web mapping; Applications; COVID-19; Literature review

1. Introduction

Since early 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has been a substantial threat to public health worldwide. COVID-19 is caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (1). The virus quickly spread to other countries in eastern Asia, Europe, and the remainder of the world (2). As of 05 July 2023, a total of 768,983,095 confirmed cases of COVID-19 including 6,953,743 deaths were reported to World Health Organization (3). It is therefore, applications offered by GIS play important roles for understanding the COVID-19 pandemic.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) is a suite of software tools for mapping and analyzing data which is georeferenced (assigned a specific location on the surface of the Earth, otherwise known as geospatial data). GIS can be used to detect geographic patterns in other data, such as disease clusters resulting from toxins, sub-optimal water access, etc. GIS has been commonly used for monitoring and management of natural resources (4–7), environment (8–10) and climate change (11,12). The applications of GIS have been widely applied in health sciences such as effective and fast decision making (13,14), prediction and analysis of diseases (15,16), management of health programs (17,18), diseases (19,20) and environmental health (21,22), accessing mental health services (23,24), disease mapping (25,26), and investigating epidemics (27,28). For instance, there have been attempts to investigate the use of GIS in disease

* Corresponding author: Thi-Quynh Nguyen ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-9868-4695>

studies such as the analysis the geography of disease (29) and in the study of the global distribution of infectious diseases (30).

The objective of this study is to conduct a systematic literature review of applications offered by GIS to help address different issues related to the study of the COVID-19 pandemic. The content is presented under three sub-sections; namely the use of GIS for mapping COVID-19, investigating of the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economies and environment, and the assessment of the community vulnerability and risks during the pandemic.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials

In this study, a total of 50 scientific papers collected from Web of Science, SCOPUS, and Google scholar databases was used. These were mostly high impact and were mainly published in recent years after the COVID-19 outbreak.

2.2. Methods

We firstly queried Web of Science, Google Scholar, and SCOPUS databases with different combinations of keywords including ‘GIS’ or ‘Geographic Information System’, ‘spatial analysis’, ‘mapping’ or ‘WebGIS’, ‘COVID-19’ or ‘SARS-CoV-2’, ‘the COVID-19 pandemic’, ‘applications’ or ‘the use’, and ‘review’ or ‘overview’. Four different sub-topics was then identified based on applications of geospatial techniques including GIS, remote sensing, GPS and Internet mapping technologies in the study of the COVID-19 pandemic. Finally, different types of applications of geospatial techniques in the study of COVID-19 were summarised and discussed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Mapping the spatial distribution of the COVID-19 pandemic

GIS tools can map and visualize the relationship between location coordinates and COVID-19 pandemic (31). One of the first example of WebGIS application during this pandemic is the web-based near-real-time COVID dashboard created by the Johns Hopkins University (32,33) . Later the WHO and different local and regional governing bodies also followed the same direction (3).

Figure 1 An example of using spatial statistics to identify spatial clustering of transmitted cases in four COVID-19 waves in Vietnam (34)

A part from using WebGIS, spatial statistics have been also used for detecting COVID-19 spatial clustering and hot spots. For instance, to identify the spatio-temporal clustering of COVID-19 hot spots and cold spots in Vietnam using spatial statistics. The local Getis-Ord’s G_i^* statistic was successfully applied to detect hotspots and coldspots of COVID-19 cases in four waves in Vietnam. The results showed that seven hotspots of COVID-19 cases in provinces were detected in areas

of high population density in the north-eastern region of Vietnam (Figure 1). Also in Vietnam, the local Moran's I spatial statistic and Moran scatterplot were successfully employed to identify high-high and low-low clusters and low-high and high-low outliers of COVID-19 cases from a dataset of 10,742 locally transmitted cases in four COVID-19 waves in 63 prefecture-level cities/provinces in Vietnam (Figure 1) (34). A Moran's I autocorrelation and spatial cluster analysis for identifying Coronavirus disease COVID-19 using GIS approach was also successfully carried out in Iraq (35).

3.2. Investigating impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economies and environment

Since the COVID-19 pandemic spread globally, the social-economies and environment of almost all countries were badly affected (36). Accordingly, attempts have been made on the use of GIS in the study of impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on social and economic activities and environment. For instance, a GIS-based spatiotemporal modelling of urban traffic accidents during the COVID-19 pandemic was successfully carried out in Tabriz City, the capital of East Azerbaijan province, north-west Iran (37).

As for environment change, the effects of lockdown on environmental degradation during the pandemic in Kabul city, the capital of Afghanistan, were also monitored using geospatial data and a statistical model of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (38). A recent study of (39) has investigated long-term effects of COVID-19, and its impact on business, employees, and CO₂ emissions, using Arc-GIS Survey 123 and Arc-GIS mapping. Similar findings were also reported by that, there were many positive environmental impacts during the COVID-19 lockdown, such as the reduction in air pollutant emissions (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, PM, NO₂, O₃, CO, and SO₂) globally (40).

Figure 2 An example of using GIS to identify the intensity of environmental quality degradation over the Kabul city: a before COVID-19 (left) and during the lockdown (right)

3.3. Assessing the community vulnerability and risks during the COVID-19 pandemic

With the main advantage of spatial analysis, GIS has been widely employed to assess the COVID-19 vulnerability in many countries over the world. For instance, in Palestine, the COVID-19 vulnerability map for the West Bank was successfully developed using the combination of Analytical Hierarchy Process, GIS, multi-criteria decision analysis and some selected potential criteria including population, population density, elderly population, accommodation and food service activities, school students, chronic diseases, hospital beds, health insurance, and pharmacy (41) (Figure 3).

Through geographic information system, attempts were also made to model the COVID-19 vulnerability using an integrated fuzzy multi-criteria decision-making approach, namely fuzzy-analytical hierarchy process and fuzzy-technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution for West Bengal in India, (42). Also with the help of GIS, the analysis of vulnerability to COVID-19 occurrence was also successfully carried out in other countries such as in the

United States (43), Ethiopia (44), Algeria (45), and México (46). A part from vulnerability assessment, a GIS-based spatial modeling approach was adopted to identify of risk factors contributing to COVID-19 incidence rates in Bangladesh (47), India (48) and other severely COVID-19 affected countries (48–50).

Figure 3 An example of using GIS for COVID-19 vulnerability map for the West Bank in Palestine (41)

4. Conclusion

To overcome limitation of recent studies in reviewing the applications of GIS in the study of COVID-19 pandemic, this work is a synthesis on the wide range of applications offered by GIS in COVID-19 studies. A total of 50 research articles related to applications of GIS were systematically retrieved and reviewed. The content was presented under three sub-sections; namely

- The use of GIS for mapping COVID-19,
- How to assess the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on socio-economies and environment, and
- The assessment of the community vulnerability and risks during the pandemic.

It was found that GIS shows great importance in the study of COVID-19 The wide range of applications offered by GIS could significantly improve how we fight the COVID pandemic. This study confirms the effectiveness of GIS in the study of the COVID-19 pandemic. This review provides new reflections and facilitates the development and improvement of GIS to study COVID-19.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors thank editors and anonymous reviewers for their valuable and constructive comments and suggestions on this paper that have helped to greatly improve the quality of the paper.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Shi Z, Chen H, Fan K, Chen P. Some thoughts and strategies of planning for the impact of “COVID-19” epidemic in Yunnan plateau basin. In: E3S Web of Conferences. EDP Sciences; 2020. p. 3044.
- [2] Spagnuolo G, De Vito D, Rengo S, Tatullo M. COVID-19 outbreak: an overview on dentistry. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(6):2094.
- [3] WHO. WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard [Internet]. 2023. Available from: <https://covid19.who.int/>
- [4] Arabameri A, Rezaei K, Cerda A, Lombardo L, Rodrigo-Comino J. GIS-based groundwater potential mapping in Shahroud plain, Iran. A comparison among statistical (bivariate and multivariate), data mining and MCDM approaches. *Sci Total Environ*. 2019;658:160–77.
- [5] Nguyen TT. Fractional vegetation cover change detection in megacities using landsat time-series images: A case study of Hanoi city (Vietnam) during 1986-2019. *Geogr Environ Sustain*. 2019;12(4).
- [6] Nguyen TT, Vu TD. Identification of multivariate geochemical anomalies using spatial autocorrelation analysis and robust statistics. *Ore Geol Rev*. 2019;111.
- [7] Nguyen TT, Vu DT, Trinh LH, Le Hang Nguyen T. Spatial cluster and outlier identification of geochemical association of elements: A case study in juirui copper mining area. *Bull Miner Res Explor*. 2016;2016(153).
- [8] Nguyen TT. Landsat time-series images-based urban heat island analysis: The effects of changes in vegetation and built-up land on land surface temperature in summer in the hanoi metropolitan area, Vietnam. *Environ Nat Resour J*. 2020;18(2).
- [9] Halder B, Bandyopadhyay J, Banik P. Monitoring the effect of urban development on urban heat island based on remote sensing and geo-spatial approach in Kolkata and adjacent areas, India. *Sustain Cities Soc*. 2021;74:103186.
- [10] Wang D, Zhang F, Yang S, Xia N, Ariken M. Exploring the spatial-temporal characteristics of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) in Central Asia based on the moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS). *Environ Monit Assess*. 2020;192:1–15.
- [11] Field CB, Barros V, Stocker TF, Dahe Q. Managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation: special report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change. Cambridge University Press; 2012.
- [12] Tehrany MS, Pradhan B, Jebur MN. Flood susceptibility analysis and its verification using a novel ensemble support vector machine and frequency ratio method. *Stoch Environ Res risk Assess*. 2015;29:1149–65.
- [13] Bédard Y, Gosselin P, Rivest S, Proulx M-J, Nadeau M, Lebel G, et al. Integrating GIS components with knowledge discovery technology for environmental health decision support. *Int J Med Inform*. 2003;70(1):79–94.
- [14] Parvin F, Ali SA, Hashmi SNI, Khatoon A. Accessibility and site suitability for healthcare services using GIS-based hybrid decision-making approach: a study in Murshidabad, India. *Spat Inf Res*. 2021;29:1–18.
- [15] Palaniyandi M. The role of remote sensing and GIS for spatial prediction of vector-borne diseases transmission: a systematic review. *J Vector Borne Dis*. 2012;49(4):197.
- [16] Hijmans RJ, Forbes GA, Walker TS. Estimating the global severity of potato late blight with GIS-linked disease forecast models. *Plant Pathol*. 2000;49(6):697–705.
- [17] Loslier L. Geographical information systems (GIS) from a health perspective. sous la Dir D Savigny P Wijeyaratne, *GIS Heal Environ*. 1995;13–20.
- [18] Fradelos EC, Papatnasiou I V, Mitsi D, Tsaras K, Kleisiaris CF, Kourkouta L. Health based geographic information systems (GIS) and their applications. *Acta Inform Medica*. 2014;22(6):402.
- [19] Ranjan R, Vinayak S. Application of remote sensing and GIS in plant disease management. *TTPP*. 2020;509.
- [20] Kuznetsov I, Panidi E, Kolesnikov A, Kikin P, Korovka V, Galkin V. GIS-based infectious disease data management on a city scale, case study of St. Petersburg, Russia. *Int Arch Photogramm Remote Sens Spat Inf Sci*. 2020;43:1463–7.
- [21] Kistemann T, Dangendorf F, Schweikart J. New perspectives on the use of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) in environmental health sciences. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2002;205(3):169–81.

- [22] Tim US. The application of GIS in environmental health sciences: opportunities and limitations. *Environ Res.* 1995;71(2):75–88.
- [23] Smith CD, Mennis J. Peer reviewed: incorporating geographic information science and technology in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Prev Chronic Dis.* 2020;17.
- [24] Higgs G. A literature review of the use of GIS-based measures of access to health care services. *Heal Serv Outcomes Res Methodol.* 2004;5:119–39.
- [25] Gao S, Mioc D, Anton F, Yi X, Coleman DJ. Online GIS services for mapping and sharing disease information. *Int J Health Geogr.* 2008;7:1–12.
- [26] Murad A, Khashoggi BF. Using GIS for disease mapping and clustering in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *ISPRS Int J Geo-Information.* 2020;9(5):328.
- [27] Rytönen MJP. Not all maps are equal: GIS and spatial analysis in epidemiology. *Int J Circumpolar Health.* 2004;63(1):9–24.
- [28] Gay E, Barnouin J. A nation-wide epidemiological study of acute bovine respiratory disease in France. *Prev Vet Med.* 2009;89(3–4):265–71.
- [29] Cromley EK. GIS and disease. *Annu Rev Public Health.* 2003;24(1):7–24.
- [30] Rogers DJ, Randolph SE. Studying the global distribution of infectious diseases using GIS and RS. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2003;1(3):231–7.
- [31] Hswen Y, Nguemdjo U, Yom-Tov E, Marcus GM, Ventelou B. Individuals' willingness to provide geospatial global positioning system (GPS) data from their smartphone during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun.* 2022;9(1):1–8.
- [32] Aristizábal-Torres D, Peñuela-Meneses CA, Barrera-Rodríguez AM. An interactive web-based dashboard to track COVID-19 in Colombia. Case study: five main cities. *Rev Salud Pública.* 2023;22:214–9.
- [33] Dong E, Du H, Gardner L. An interactive web-based dashboard to track COVID-19 in real time. *Lancet Infect Dis.* 2020;20(5):533–4.
- [34] Hoang A, Nguyen T. Identifying Spatio-Temporal Clustering of the COVID-19 Patterns Using Spatial Statistics: Case Studies of Four Waves in Vietnam. *Int J Appl Geospatial Res.* 2022;13(1):1–15.
- [35] Jaber AS, Hussein AK, Kadhim NA, Bojassim AA. A Moran's I autocorrelation and spatial cluster analysis for identifying Coronavirus disease COVID-19 in Iraq using GIS approach. *Casp J Environ Sci.* 2022;20(1):55–60.
- [36] Maital S, Barzani E. The global economic impact of COVID-19: A summary of research. *Samuel Neaman Inst Natl Policy Res.* 2020;2020:1–12.
- [37] Feizizadeh B, Omarzadeh D, Sharifi A, Rahmani A, Lakes T, Blaschke T. A GIS-based spatiotemporal modelling of urban traffic accidents in Tabriz City during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Sustainability.* 2022;14(12):7468.
- [38] Ahmadi H, Sahak AS, Ayoobi AW, Pekkan E, Inceoğlu M, Karsli F. Application of GIS-Based AHP Model for the Impact Assessment of COVID-19 Lockdown on Environment Quality: The Case of Kabul City, Afghanistan. *J Indian Soc Remote Sens.* 2023;51(3):439–52.
- [39] Gary V, Sarah S, Deborah N. Long-Term Effects of COVID-19, and Its Impact on Business, Employees, and CO2 Emissions, a Study Using Arc-GIS Survey 123 and Arc-GIS Mapping. *Sustainability.* 2022;14(20):13689.
- [40] Mashayekhi R, Pavlovic R, Racine J, Moran MD, Manseau PM, Duhamel A, et al. Isolating the impact of COVID-19 lockdown measures on urban air quality in Canada. *Air Qual Atmos Heal.* 2021;14(10):1549–70.
- [41] Shadeed S, Alawna S. GIS-based COVID-19 vulnerability mapping in the West Bank, Palestine. *Int J Disaster Risk Reduct.* 2021;64:102483.
- [42] Malakar S. Geospatial modelling of COVID-19 vulnerability using an integrated fuzzy MCDM approach: a case study of West Bengal, India. *Model Earth Syst Environ.* 2022;8(3):3103–16.
- [43] Ali T, Mortula M, Sadiq R. GIS-based vulnerability analysis of the United States to COVID-19 occurrence. *J Risk Res.* 2021;24(3–4):416–31.
- [44] Asfaw H, Karuppanan S, Erduno T, Almohamad H, Dughairi AA Al, Al-Mutiry M, et al. Evaluation of Vulnerability Status of the Infection Risk to COVID-19 Using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA): A Case Study of Addis Ababa City, Ethiopia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022;19(13):7811.

- [45] Kalla MI, Lahmar B, Geullouh S, Kalla M. Health geo-governance to assess the vulnerability of Batna, Algeria to COVID-19: The role of GIS in the fight against a pandemic. *GeoJournal*. 2022;87(5):3607–20.
- [46] Sánchez-Sánchez JA, Chuc VMK, Canché EAR, Uscanga FJL. Vulnerability assessing contagion risk of Covid-19 using geographic information systems and multi-criteria decision analysis: Case study Chetumal, México. In: *GIS LATAM: First Conference, GIS LATAM 2020, Mexico City, Mexico, September 28–30, 2020, Proceedings 1*. Springer; 2020. p. 1–17.
- [47] Rahman MH, Zafri NM, Ashik FR, Waliullah M, Khan A. Identification of risk factors contributing to COVID-19 incidence rates in Bangladesh: A GIS-based spatial modeling approach. *Heliyon*. 2021;7(2).
- [48] Kanga S, Meraj G, Sudhanshu, Farooq M, Nathawat MS, Singh SK. Analyzing the risk to COVID-19 infection using remote sensing and GIS. *Risk Anal*. 2021;41(5):801–13.
- [49] Nath B, Majumder S, Sen J, Rahman MM. Risk analysis of COVID-19 infections in Kolkata Metropolitan city: A GIS-based study and policy implications. *GeoHealth*. 2021;5(4):e2020GH000368.
- [50] Kanga S, Meraj G, Farooq M, Nathawat MS, Singh SK. Risk assessment to curb COVID-19 contagion: A preliminary study using remote sensing and GIS. 2020.